

Music Therapy Research In India: A Review

Deepa Iyer S¹, Dr. Rajshri Ramakrishna²

¹Ph.D Scholar, Department of Indian Music, ²Associate Professor, Department of Indian Music, University of Madras, Chepauk, Chennai - 600 005

Abstract:

While the impact of sound and music on both mental and physical health and wellbeing has been recognized since ancient times, the field of music therapy is currently in its developmental stages, with active research gaining momentum only in the last decade. This paper aims to present a descriptive review of music therapy research in India, providing an overview of the existing literature, examining the therapeutic application of music in diverse cultural and clinical settings. The review examines the effectiveness of music therapy in addressing various conditions, including physiological, mental health, rehabilitation settings and overall well being.

Additionally, the paper explores the impact of cultural factors on the practice of music therapy in India, including the incorporation of traditional musical elements and indigenous healing practices. Emphasising on the current developmental stage of music therapy as a field of study, the paper sheds light on the recent surge in research activities, contributing to the evolving landscape of music therapy in India.

Keywords: Music Therapy, Literature Review, Indian Music, therapeutic applications, Descriptive review, Indian Music Therapy

Introduction:

Music therapy, defined as the professional application of music and its elements as an intervention in various settings, has garnered attention across medical, educational, and everyday environments. The purpose is to enhance the quality of life and address diverse aspects of health and well-being, including physical, social, communicative, emotional, intellectual, and spiritual dimensions (WFMT, 2011). References to music therapy practices

in India trace back to ancient times, evident in Vēdic traditions, āyurvēda, Yōga, and cultural contexts.

The roots of music therapy in India are embedded in musicological texts, such as Lakṣaṇa Grantha-s, which expound on the essentials of music and delve into the concept of music therapy in the Indian context. Despite the longstanding awareness of the therapeutic effects of music, the formal field of music therapy in India is presently undergoing developmental stages. Only in the last decade has active research gained momentum, signifying a nascent but expanding area of study within the broader landscape of healthcare practices.

Methodology:

The descriptive review was conducted using online database PubMed using the keywords “Music Therapy”, “Music Therapy in India” and “Indian Music Therapy”. To refine the scope of the considered studies, inclusion and exclusion criteria were systematically applied.

- *Inclusion Criteria:*

1. Papers Written in English
2. Papers written from 2013 - 2023
3. Clinical Trials or Randomised Control Trials
4. Full Text Availability
5. Studies conducted in India

- *Exclusion Criteria:*

1. Duplicated Papers
2. Literature Reviews and Historical Studies

Initially, papers deemed irrelevant were excluded through a manual screening of titles and abstracts. Subsequently, a thorough reading of the remaining articles was done to eliminate any additional studies that were found to be irrelevant or inappropriate. The final selection of studies was then identified, read, analysed, and reviewed.

Discussion

The research papers selected for inclusion in the review (n=12), have been reviewed and their findings are elucidated in this section in a chronological order.

A randomised controlled trial aimed to evaluate the impact of passive listening to relaxing Rāga on the autonomic functions of prehypertensive and stage I hypertensive individuals. A hundred participants were randomly assigned to two groups: Group 1 received music intervention alongside lifestyle modifications, listening to Rāga Bhīmpalāsi played on flute for 15 minutes daily for three months, while Group 2 received only lifestyle modifications. Results showed a significant reduction in stress levels, diastolic blood pressure, and systolic blood pressure in Group 1. Both groups exhibited an insignificant rise in parasympathetic parameters of heart rate variability, while significantly increased parasympathetic and lower sympathetic parameters were observed in both male and female participants of Group 1 and 2. The study concludes that passive listening to Indian music, when combined with lifestyle modifications, has a role in normalising blood pressure through autonomic function modification, suggesting its potential as a complementary therapy for hypertension management. (Kunikullaya, K. U., et al. 2015)

A quantitative study published in the Indian Journal of Palliative Care conducted on cancer patients with moderate to severe pain, music therapy was shown to significantly reduce pain scores in the test group receiving music therapy, as compared to the control group engaged in conversation. Although the reduction in anxiety levels was not statistically

significant in both groups, the results suggest that music therapy can be an effective addition to standard palliative care for pain management, emphasising the need for larger-scale studies to establish its role in holistic palliative care strategies. (Krishnaswamy, Priyadharshini, 2016)

Two separate studies explored the therapeutic potential of music interventions in healthcare settings. The first study, a randomised controlled trial, investigated the use of music therapy to reduce dental anxiety in paediatric patients aged 4-6 years. The results showed that both Bach flower therapy (BFT) and music therapy (MT) significantly decreased dental anxiety, with the BFT group demonstrating notably better behaviour than the control group. The second study, also a randomised controlled trial, assessed the effects of music intervention in combination with lifestyle modifications on blood pressure (BP) in individuals with prehypertension or stage I hypertension. The findings revealed that passive listening to relaxing Rāga music, along with lifestyle modifications, positively impacted autonomic functions and significantly reduced stress levels and BP, indicating its potential as a complementary therapy for hypertension management. These studies underscore the therapeutic benefits of music interventions in healthcare, ranging from anxiety reduction in paediatric dentistry to BP control in hypertensive individuals. (Kunikullaya, Kirthana Ubrangala et al.2015), (Kunikullaya, Kirthana Ubrangala et al.2016)

A randomised controlled trial conducted in a Level-3 University-affiliated neonatal intensive care unit, the efficacy of pain control interventions in preterm neonates undergoing heel-prick for glucose assessment was evaluated. Among the interventions - Kangaroo mother care (KMC) with Music therapy, Music therapy alone, Kangaroo Mother care without music, and Control (no additional intervention) - KMC with and without Music therapy significantly reduced pain, as measured by the Premature Infant Pain Profile (PIPP) scores, compared to the Control group. Both KMC groups showed lower PIPP scores than the

Control group, emphasising the effectiveness of Kangaroo mother care as a primary method for pain control in preterm neonates undergoing heel-prick. The study highlights the tangible benefits of incorporating music therapy as part of Kangaroo mother care in alleviating pain during medical procedures in this vulnerable population. (Shukla, V. V., Bansal, S., et al. 2018)

The study aimed to assess the impact of music therapy on children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD). A total of 30 children with ASD were divided into two groups: one receiving music therapy in addition to their standard treatment, and the other following their standard treatment alone. The study found that the group receiving music therapy exhibited significant improvements in social skills, communication, and overall behaviour compared to the control group. These findings suggest that music therapy can be a valuable complementary intervention for children with ASD to enhance their social and communication abilities and behavioural outcomes (Bharathi, Geetha et al. 2019).

This study aimed to compare the effectiveness of Bach flower therapy (BFT) and music therapy (MT) in reducing dental anxiety in paediatric patients aged 4-6 years. The results showed that both BFT and MT significantly reduced dental anxiety in these children, with the BFT group exhibiting notably better behaviour than the control group. While postoperative anxiety scores did not differ significantly, both BFT and MT groups experienced reduced pulse rates during treatment. MT was particularly effective in lowering systolic blood pressure, and the control group had an increase in diastolic blood pressure. These findings suggest that BFT and MT can be valuable tools in alleviating dental anxiety in young patients (Dixit, Uma B, and Rishita R, 2020)

A study published in Explore NY, aimed to investigate the anxiolytic effect of lower-level musical properties, such as tempo and octave variations, in Carnatic music

concerts. A randomised controlled cross-over study involving 21 male undergraduate medical students was conducted. Participants listened to "Varying music" (VM), which included incremental variations in tempo and octave, and "Stable music" (SM), without such variations, three times daily for six days. Both types of music were recorded in Rāga Kāpi, and silence served as the control intervention. The study employed Electroencephalography (EEG) and Electrocardiography (for heart rate variability) on all six days and assessed anxiety levels using Beck's Anxiety Inventory and State-Trait Anxiety Scale on Day 1 and Day 6. The results showed a significant reduction in anxiety scores in the VM group, with notable differences in EEG power and brain activation patterns between the VM and SM groups. VM induced a state of 'controlled-mind wandering,' involving balanced transitions between heightened self-attention and reduced mind wandering, while SM showed greater right brain activation. Importantly, heart rate variability remained stable during both music interventions. These findings suggest that the choice of music has a significant impact on stress management, highlighting the need for further research in this area. (Sharma, Sushma et al. 2021)

In a prospective randomised controlled trial at the Aravind Eye Care System in Pondicherry, India, assessing the impact of preoperative and perioperative music exposure on first-time phacoemulsification cataract surgery, significant reductions in self-reported anxiety levels were observed among the 165 patients who received music. Prior to music exposure, 38% reported high anxiety, which dropped to 4% after 10 minutes of music. During the perioperative period, 48% of the music group felt not at all or a little anxious compared to 30% in the control group. Postoperatively, 84% of the music group reported feeling not at all or a little anxious, in contrast to 56% in the control group. Importantly, the music group exhibited a statistically significant decrease in postoperative blood pressure, highlighting the

potential of music as a cost-effective and efficient means to alleviate anxiety and enhance the overall patient experience in high-volume cataract surgery settings.(Muddana, S. K., et. al. 2021)

Music therapy has shown promise in reducing pain, stress, and improving neuro-developmental outcomes in newborns. In a randomised controlled trial conducted at the neonatal intensive care unit of Burdwan Medical College, West Bengal, 3095 newborns with birth asphyxia were assigned to two groups: one receiving music therapy alongside conventional management (Group A), and the other receiving conventional management only (Group B). Group A exhibited reduced hospital stay, lower oxygen dependency, fewer instances of apnea, and decreased pain during procedures, in addition to achieving better mental and motor neuro-developmental quotients. While these results suggest the potential benefits of music therapy, further multi-centric research is needed before generalising the findings (Konar, Mithun Chandra et al. 2021).

Among various non-pharmacologic approaches to alleviate perioperative anxiety in patients undergoing orthopaedic surgeries under spinal anaesthesia, this randomised control trial conducted at a tertiary care hospital assessed the impact of music therapy. The study found that patients who listened to standard relaxation music (group M) experienced statistically significant reductions in heart rate and respiratory rate compared to those exposed to standard operation theatre noise (group C). Furthermore, patients in the music group reported higher satisfaction levels. These results indicate that music therapy can effectively mitigate anxiety, stabilise hemodynamics, and enhance patient satisfaction in the perioperative setting, presenting a valuable approach for improving the surgical experience (Kaur, H., et al. 2022).

In a randomised controlled trial conducted at a South Indian teaching hospital, women undergoing oocyte retrieval were assigned to receive either music therapy alongside conscious sedation (Group A) or conscious sedation alone (Group B). The study found that while post-procedure pain scores were similar between the two groups, women offered music therapy reported significantly lower anxiety levels. Thus, while music therapy may not significantly enhance pain relief during oocyte retrieval, it holds promise in reducing anxiety levels associated with the procedure (Nandeibam, Yohen et al., 2022)

Binaural beat is an illusion created by the brain when one listens to two tones with slightly different frequencies at the same time.¹ Studies suggest that Binaural beats in the alpha frequencies (8 to 13 Hz) encourage relaxation, promote positivity, and decrease anxiety. Following this claim, a study aimed to evaluate the impact of alpha binaural beat music (BBM) on pain levels post-maxillary fixed orthodontic appliance placement. In comparison to a control group, the BBM group showed a significant reduction in both sensory and psychological pain aspects after the 5th day. The placebo group exhibited lower affective and total pain scores on day 6 compared to the control. Present Pain Intensity scores were consistently lower in the BBM group from days 3 to 7, and the placebo group had lower scores on days 4, 5, and 6. The Visual Analog Scale indicated lower scores for the placebo group on day 4 and the BBM group on days 6 and 7, compared to the control. In conclusion, BBM demonstrated a notable pain reduction towards the end of the first treatment week, with no significant difference between BBM and placebo groups. (Aly, A. E. et al., 2023)

Another study conducted to assess the effectiveness of Hare Krishna Mantra Based Cognitive Therapy (HMBCT), a novel and cost-effective treatment for insomnia. The research employed a randomised controlled trial design, dividing participants into two

¹ WebMD. (n.d.). *Binaural beats: What are they and what are the benefits?*. WebMD. <https://www.webmd.com/balance/what-are-binaural-beats>

groups: one receiving HMBCT therapy and the other acting as a control group, exposed to relaxing music. Over a six-week treatment period, both groups underwent traditional cognitive-behavioural therapy techniques, including stimulus control, sleep restriction, and sleep hygiene. Notably, the results indicated significant improvements in sleep quality, with participants in the HMBCT group experiencing a 61% reduction in Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS) scores and an 80% reduction in Insomnia Severity Index (ISI) scores. These findings suggest that the integration of mantra chanting within traditional cognitive-behavioural therapy may offer a promising approach to enhancing sleep quality (Behera et al., 2023).

An open-label randomised trial published in the *International Journal of Yoga Therapy* involving frontline healthcare workers during the COVID-19 pandemic, concludes that yoga nidra practice was found to be more effective than relaxation to music in reducing depression, anxiety, and insomnia. But it is seen the study did not find a statistically significant difference between yoga nidra and relaxation to music in reducing depression, anxiety, and insomnia. These results suggest that both interventions may have limited effectiveness in improving the mental health of healthcare workers during their duty periods amidst the pandemic. (Gunjiganvi, Mallikarjun et al., 2023)

Conclusion

The studies discussed showcase the effectiveness of music therapy across domains, including pain management, paediatric dentistry, autism spectrum disorder, dental anxiety, hypertension, and perioperative care. These findings emphasise the potential of music therapy to alleviate pain, anxiety, and improve well-being at the same time collectively it highlights the impact of music in healthcare settings. It is also seen that a few studies incorporate the traditional musical elements and indigenous healing practices such as mantra-s and rāga-s. However, it's important to note that this review is based on studies available in the online

database PubMed. To gain a more comprehensive understanding of the studies related to music therapy in India, further research and exploration of additional resources and databases may be necessary.

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